

Master's thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the examination requirements of the Research Master Cognitive and Clinical Neuroscience. Specialization Neuropsychology, Maastricht University

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August the 12th 2013

Title: Neurocognitive Processes Associated with Peer Preference in Preschool Children

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Neurocognitive Processes Associated with Peer Preference in Preschool Children

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Abstract

Being liked or preferred by peers is important for human beings and more so for children. During preschool years the development of the ability to relate to peer groups takes place. At this age, being highly disliked by peers in a group may be a sign of the particular functioning of specific neurocognitive processes. This study thus explored how cognitive inhibitory control (CIC) and behavioral inhibition/behavioral activation systems (BIS/BAS) are associated with peer preference in preschool children. Twenty-nine 4-year-olds were tested with a neuropsychological measure of CIC (i.e. peg tapping task), and a neuropsychological (i.e. SPSRQ-C) and a neurophysiological (i.e. EEG frontal asymmetry) measure of BIS/BAS activity. Peer preference was measured with sociometric interviews. CIC was not associated with peer preference. In contrast, BIS was positively related with peer preference, while BAS was negatively related with peer preference. Specifically, the ‘fight/flight/freezing system’ factor of the BIS and the ‘drive’ factor of the BAS showed the significant correlation with peer preference. Furthermore, the BIS to BAS ratios proved useful to explain peer preference. No correlation was found between EEG frontal asymmetry and peer preference. The importance of considering both BIS and BAS scores is discussed. A major role of BIS/BAS, compared to CIC, in level of peer preference was concluded.

Keywords: *Peer preference, Inhibitory control, BIS/BAS, EEG frontal asymmetry, FFFS, reward responsiveness.*

Introduction

Being liked or preferred by peers is important for human beings and more so for children (Harris, 1995). People build friendships and many other social relations upon the basis of choosing those who we like or prefer. As relationships with others are necessary antecedents of attitudes toward oneself (Hartup, 1989), being preferred by others is crucial for psychological wellbeing. The development of the ability to relate to peers in groups takes place during preschool years (Hay, Payne, & Chadwick, 2004). Hence some of the children who have poor ability to relate to peers are overtly disliked and excluded from the peer group (Villanueva Badenes, Clemente Estevan, & García Bacete, 2000). Being highly disliked by peers in a group may be a sign of the particular functioning of specific neurocognitive (i.e. neuropsychological and neurophysiological) processes that qualitatively and quantitatively determine the behaviors children exhibit. Thus, it is necessary to study how neurocognitive processes are associated with a preschool child's level of social peer preference. This was the main purpose of this research.

Social peer preference is a measure of social likability that informs about the relative extent to which a child is liked or disliked by his/her peers (Coie, Dodge, & Coppotelli, 1982; Newcomb, Bukowski, & Pattee, 1993). It is not only that children are arbitrarily preferred or non-preferred. The social preference of a child within his/her peer group (i.e. 'peer preference') is an index of social competence (Rose-Krasnor, 1997). Social competence refers to the ability to effectively use or create opportunities to generate adaptive responses to social demands (Waters & Sroufe, 1983) and is context-dependent (Rose-Krasnor, 1997). Social competence is built upon different emotional, cognitive, and behavioral abilities (Domitrovich, Cortes, & Greenberg, 2007) as turn-taking, sharing, or self-regulation (Hay et al., 2004) and preschool age is a developmentally appropriate time for children to acquire them (Johnson, Ironsmith, Snow, & Poteat, 2000). Therefore, preschool children's levels of peer preference might reflect individual differences in the development of these abilities.

Specific behaviors are associated with a child's level of peer preference. Verbal and physical aggression, and approach to peers are among these behaviors (Dodge, 1983; Newcomb et al., 1993). Children with higher peer preference tend to exhibit lower levels of aggression and less approach to peers (Dodge, 1983; Newcomb et al., 1993), in addition to many positive

prosocial interactions (e.g. engaging in cooperative play, displaying positive affect, etc.; Walker, 2009). Aggression and approach/avoidance support the development of social skills required for positive interactions (Hay et al., 2004). Consequently, this study only focused on the neurocognitive processes that underlie aggression and approach/avoidance. The first one, Cognitive Inhibitory Control (CIC), is necessary to ‘put the brake’ on aggressive behaviors. The second one, Behavioral Inhibition System/Behavioral Activation System (BIS/BAS), should be balanced in order to let a child adequately avoid or approach peers. Specifically, this study explored how these neurocognitive processes are associated with peer preference in preschool children.

The first neurocognitive process studied in relation to peer preference was Cognitive Inhibitory Control (CIC). CIC is an executive function (Miller & Cohen, 2001) characterized by a willed or active process of suppression of an irrelevant response—mainly a motor response (Aron, 2007). Hence CIC is a central component of executive functioning (Morasch & Bell, 2011) associated with *top-down* control processes that involve the prefrontal cortex functioning (Aron, 2007). These top-down processes have to do with the neural signals that the prefrontal cortex sends to subcortical and posterior brain regions to modulate and direct their processing according to current demands (Ridderinkhof, van den Wildenberg, Segalowitz, & Carter, 2004), in order to accomplish a specific goal (e.g. a child who refrains from hitting other children to avoid hurting them, or being hurt or scolded). CIC has been associated with different social competence skills. For instance, high CIC has been associated with more cooperative behaviors (concurrent relation; Ciairano, Visu-Petra, & Settanni, 2007), fewer non-cooperative behaviors (i.e. lack of social competence in a predictive way; Ciairano et al., 2007; Giannotta, Burk, & Ciairano, 2011), more social skills (i.e. prosocial behavior; Rhoades, Greenberg, & Domitrovich, 2009), fewer internalizing problems (Rhoades et al., 2009), theory of mind ability (Razza & Blair, 2009), and greater ability to regulate anger and frustration (Wolfe & Bell, 2004). As children with these skills are also more preferred by their peers (Dodge, 1983; Newcomb et al., 1993), CIC should also be related with peer preference.

The second neurocognitive process studied in relation to peer preference was the Behavioral Inhibition System/Behavioral Activation System (BIS/BAS). The BIS and BAS are concepts based on behavioral neuroscience studies (e.g., Gray, 1972, 1990) that support

neurobiological models of personality (Kennis, Rademaker, & Geuze, 2013) and can be addressed through different methods (e.g. neuropsychological and neurophysiological). The BIS can be defined as a behavioral manifestation of attentional engagement to cues of punishment while stopping ongoing behavior, in order to process these cues and prepare a response (Amodio, Master, Yee, & Taylor, 2008). The BAS can be seen as a motivational system sensitive to signals of reward, important for engaging behavior toward a reward (Amodio et al., 2008). The BIS is composed of a BIS (i.e. ‘general anxiety’) factor and a Fight/Flight/Freezing System (i.e. FFFS, ‘social fear’) factor (Luman, van Meel, Oosterlaan, & Geurts, 2012). The BAS is composed of Reward Responsiveness (i.e. positive responses to the occurrence or anticipation of reward), Impulsivity/Fun Seeking (i.e. willingness to approach a potentially rewarding event on the spur of the moment), and Drive (i.e. persistent pursuit of desired goals) factors (Luman et al., 2012). The BIS, though not the BAS, has been significantly positively associated with social competence as reported by the teacher (Blair, 2003). This finding may seem counterintuitive because socially competent children should show more social overtures (i.e. high BAS) but not more anxious behavior (i.e. high BIS), which entails less approach and more passive avoidance. However, this finding has been explained as high BIS can provide young children with the possibility to avoid or peacefully resolve potential conflict situations with peers (Blair, 2003).

The BIS/BAS activity was also explored neurophysiologically (e.g. Fox, Schmidt, Calkins, Rubin, & Coplan, 1996) in its association with peer preference. Specifically, the patterns of asymmetrical activation in the electroencephalographic (EEG) alpha band (i.e. 8- to 13-Hz) recorded over the frontal region of the brain during resting state were explored. These patterns of asymmetrical frontal activation in EEG alpha-power during resting can be used as a measure of BIS/BAS activity (Sutton & Davidson, 1997). The use of EEG alpha power is driven by the fact that when sensory cortex receives incoming stimuli, the EEG alpha power over the same part of the cortex decreases in amplitude (i.e. is desynchronized; Fox et al., 1996). Thus, as increased alpha power indicates decreased cortical activity, higher asymmetry values indicate greater relative left hemisphere activation and lower asymmetry values indicate greater relative right hemisphere activation (Davidson & Tomarken, 1989). Greater relative left frontal activity has been found associated with higher BAS and—yet less consistently—with lower BIS (Amodio et al., 2008; Coan & Allen, 2003; Harmon-Jones, Gable, & Peterson, 2010; Sutton & Davidson, 1997), in accordance with initial hypotheses that approach vs. withdrawal emotional

and motivational tendencies might be the underlying dimensions indexed by asymmetries in anterior regions (Davidson & Tomarken, 1989). Consequently, greater left frontal activity (related with higher BAS) might be associated with lower peer preference.

In summary, as the level of peer preference may be a sign of the functioning of specific neurocognitive processes (i.e. CIC and BIS/BAS), this study sought to investigate how CIC (related to aggression) and BIS/BAS (related to approach/avoidance) are associated with peer preference in preschool children. Therefore this study first examined how CIC and BIS/BAS are independently related with peer preference in preschool children. For CIC, as social competence skills are associated with high CIC, a positive correlation was expected between CIC and peer preference. For BIS/BAS, as a balance should be seen, a positive correlation between BIS and peer preference and a negative correlation between BAS and peer preference were expected. Moreover, as BAS is associated with greater relative left frontal activity, this latter was expected to be negatively associated with peer preference. Second, this study explored which of both neurocognitive processes (CIC or BIS/BAS) better predict peer preference.

Method

Participants

Twenty-nine 4-year-olds (19 girls; 65%) participated in this study. This sample was drawn from a longitudinal sample of an ongoing 2.5-year longitudinal project in the Baby Research in Action, Interaction, and Neurocognition (Baby-BRAIN) group at the Donders Institute (Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen). The only inclusion criterion was to have complete data on all of the previous measurements of the longitudinal study. The mean age of the participants was 52.40 months (SD: 1.98; range: 49.1 — 55.2 months) old. The parents of all the participating children gave informed consent for the participation of their children in the longitudinal study. Children also gave their verbal assent.

Instruments

Peer Preference. To establish the peer preference score of the participants, sociometric interviews were conducted. In a sociometric interview each child is shown pictures of all the other children in their class and asked to rate whether they like, do not like, or sometimes like but

sometimes do not like to play with each classmate (Asher, Singleton, Tinsley, & Hymel, 1979). Children see the pictures, one by one, of all the classmates. Children are instructed to click on a smiling face if they “like to play with (Jip),” on a sad face if they “don’t like to play with (Jip),” or on a neutral face if they “sometimes like to play with (Jip) but sometimes not.” The pictures of all the other classmates (and not only of the child of interest for this study) were shown to make the situation as natural as possible and more alike to a game. A sociometric score of peer preference can be derived from this procedure. Specifically, the number of ratings received from all classmates for ‘Like’ and for ‘Dislike’ only are standardized within the school class and transformed into one new variable, ‘social preference’ (i.e. called peer preference in this study). Social preference is calculated as the difference between the standardized Like and the standardized Dislike number of ratings (Coie & Dodge, 1983). The resulting difference score is also standardized within the class. Thus, the lower (i.e. more negative) the Z-score, the lower is the peer preference of the participant, and the higher (i.e. more positive) the Z-score, the higher is the peer preference of the participant.

Cognitive Inhibitory Control. Luria’s peg tapping task (Luria, 1966) was used to measure CIC. Immediately after the experimenter taps once with a dowel (22.5 cm long, 2.5 cm in diameter, see Figure 1) the child is to tap twice with the dowel, and immediately after the experimenter taps twice the child is to tap once. A session consists of a pseudorandom series of 16 trials, each trial composed of the experimenter’s tap(s) and the child’s response. The experimenter taps and then hands in the dowel to the child for a response, after which the child returns the dowel to the experimenter (Diamond & Taylor, 1996). The percentage of correct responses is used as the measure of inhibitory control. In order to have a reliable measure of CIC, participants should have at least completed 4 trials. The task was scored from the video recordings of the measurement session.

Figure 1. Dowel used for Luria’s Peg Tapping Task.

Behavioral Inhibition System/Behavioral Activation System. The Dutch version for parent report (ages 6 to 13; Luman et al., 2012) of the Sensitivity to Punishment and Sensitivity to Reward Questionnaire for Children (SPSRQ-C; Colder & O'Connor, 2004) was one of the two measures of BIS/BAS used (also see [Appendix](#)). The questionnaire contains in total 33 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale (e.g. 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) and consists of two scales, sensitivity to punishment (i.e. BIS) and sensitivity to reward (i.e. BAS). The Sensitivity to Punishment scale consists of 15 items that measure two factors, namely, FFFS (Fight/Flight/Freeze System) and BIS. The Sensitivity to Reward scale consists of 18 items that measure three factors, namely, Reward Responsiveness (REWRESP; 7 items), Impulsivity/Fun-Seeking (IMPFUN; 7 items), and Drive (4 items). Coefficient alphas of the 5-factor model are 0.79 for FFFS, 0.76 for BIS, 0.78 for REWRESP, 0.70 for IMPFUN, and 0.65 for Drive (Luman et al., 2012). Moreover, ratios between the scores (i.e. BIS to BAS) were used based on the rationale of considering one score (BIS) *in relation to or taking into account* the other (BAS). Importantly, although this version of the SPSRQ-C is not special for preschool children (i.e. 4-6 year-olds), parents did not report difficulties with the items during the piloting of the study. However, a second BIS/BAS measure was also used.

The second measure of BIS/BAS was the EEG frontal asymmetry value (AsymF), which is derived from the EEG alpha power at frontal sites of the scalp (i.e. F3, F7 for left and F4, F8 for right) during resting state. During resting state six different videos that showed non-biological movement (e.g. colorful shining stars and colorful checkerboards) were presented, and to which children were instructed to attend while sitting still (as is done in other studies with preschool children, e.g. Fox et al., 1995; Fox et al., 1996). Each video was presented three consecutive times and each lasted 8000 msec. with an ISI of 1000 msec during which a fixation cross was presented. As these videos were the baseline of a different study (i.e. an action perception study), each one of them was presented every two action-observation videos (i.e. six in total) that required focusing either on an action performed or on the color of the objects used to perform the action. Electrophysiological recordings were conducted using child-sized EEG caps with 32 electrode sites on the scalp. The Ag/AgCl active electrodes were placed in an actiCap (Brain Products, Munich), arranged in the 10-20 system, referenced online to electrode FCz over the central midline and re-referenced offline to the average of all electrode sites. A small amount of abrasive gel was put into each electrode site while impedances were checked.

Impedances were accepted if they were less than or equal to 20 K Ω . The EEG signal was amplified using a 32-channel BrainAmp DC EEG amplifier, band-pass filtered (.1-125 Hz), and digitized at a sampling rate of 500 Hz.

Procedure

As almost all of the participating children attended to different schools, they were visited in their respective schools. All of their classmates (including the participants themselves) were interviewed for the sociometric measure. After the pictures of every classmate were taken and set in a computer, every child of the class was escorted to a room. Children saw on the computer the pictures of all of their classmates who had been granted permission by their parents to participate and who were present that day (including the child of interest). If the participating child was unexpectedly not present, a picture was provided from the school records. In a separate session one to four weeks apart, the participating children went to the EEG lab for a different study about action perception from which baseline data were taken. After the EEG measurement, children were administered Luria's peg tapping task (i.e. CIC measure) while being unobtrusively video-recorded. All participants' parents brought the Sensitivity to Punishment and Sensitivity to Reward Questionnaire for Children (SPSRQ-C) already filled out, as it had been sent together with the letter of invitation and the consent form for the EEG experiment.

Data Analysis

The peer preference scores (i.e. the dependent variable of this study), the CIC measure, all BIS/BAS factors of the SPSRQ-C and their ratio, and the EEG frontal asymmetry power (i.e. independent variables of this study) were calculated. Two participants were excluded from the analyses involving the CIC measure because they did not wish to do the task. Three different participants were excluded from the EEG analysis due to excessive movement or EEG artifacts. One participant was excluded from both analyses. None of the participants excluded differed from the participants included in any other variable. To accomplish the first goal of this study, Pearson correlation coefficients were computed between the independent and the dependent variables. For the second goal, stepwise regression analyses were conducted using all of the independent variables, age, and gender as predictors.

EEG Data Analysis. Electroencephalographic (EEG) data were analyzed using FieldTrip (Oostenveld, Fries, Maris, & Schoffelen, 2011), an open source Matlab toolbox (Donders Institute, Nijmegen). The EEG data were locked to the start of each movie and segmented into eight 1-second-segments (i.e. further referred to as trials). Video recordings of the measurement session were used to code behavior and reject trials in which children either moved or did not look at the screen during the presentation of the videos. A visual inspection of the remaining trials was also conducted to exclude EEG artifacts (e.g. noisy channels or eye blinks). Participants with fewer than 10 trials (i.e. fewer than 10 s of artifact-free EEG; Davidson & Tomarken, 1989) were excluded from the analyses ($N = 4$). Participants with more than 10 trials had on average 32 trials (range: 11 – 55) of baseline. A Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was performed on all artifact-free 1-s chunks of data (extracted through overlapping Hamming windows) to derive estimates of spectral power (μV^2) in the 8- to 13-Hz frequency band for each frontal electrode site (i.e. F3, F4, F7, and F8). The alpha power was then averaged per side (i.e. F3 and F7 for left, and F4 and F8 for right) and log-transformed using the natural log (\ln) to normalize the distribution. Finally, the EEG frontal asymmetry value (AsymF) was calculated subtracting the \ln of the averaged left frontal power from the \ln of the averaged right frontal power (i.e. \ln right frontal - \ln left frontal; Davidson & Tomarken, 1989).

Results

Behavioral Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of all the variables of interest for the overall sample are shown in Table 1. Preliminary *t*-tests indicated that boys and girls did not significantly differ in any of the predictor or the outcome variables. The mean peer preference *Z*-score indicates that this sample of preschool children had an average peer preference; in other words, this sample was neither overtly liked nor overtly disliked, which is adequate to explore individual differences. Likewise, the mean score for CIC is within the expected score for 4-year-olds (Diamond & Taylor, 1996). Similarly, the scores for all of the BIS and BAS factors fall within the range for typically developing children (cf. Luman et al., 2012).

Table 1. Main results of the overall sample in all of the variables of interest of the study.

Variable	<i>N</i>	Mean (SD)	Range
1. Peer preference (Z score)	29	-0.53 (1.06)	-2.95 — 1.36
2. CIC (Luria’s peg tapping task)			
Total completed trials / 16	26	14.62 (2.58)	6 — 16
Percentage correct trials	26	79.23% (19.56%)	38% — 100%
3. BIS (Sensitivity to Punishment SPSRQ-C)			
Fight/Flight/Freeze System / 5	29	2.28 (0.61)	1.13 — 3.75
Behavioral Inhibition System / 5	29	2.55 (0.35)	1.89 — 3.22
4. BAS (Sensitivity to Reward SPSRQ-C)			
Reward Responsiveness / 5	29	3.42 (0.60)	2.17 — 4.50
Impulsiveness/Fun Seeking / 5	29	2.21 (0.53)	1.25 — 3.25
Drive / 5	29	3.25 (0.55)	2.33 — 4.17

CIC: Cognitive Inhibitory Control; BIS: Behavioral Inhibition System; BAS: Behavioral Activation System; SPSRQ-C: Children version of the Sensitivity to Punishment and Sensitivity to Reward Questionnaire.

EEG Descriptive Statistics

The EEG frontal alpha-power asymmetry during baseline (AsymF; ‘right hemisphere frontal alpha power — left hemisphere frontal alpha power’) was explored in this sample too. A high or positive AsymF means greater relative left-frontal activation (Davidson & Tomarken, 1989). A low or negative AsymF in turn means greater relative right-frontal activation. The EEG frontal power asymmetry descriptive values during baseline (AsymF), as well as the values from which they are derived (i.e. average of electrode sites per side) for the overall sample, are presented in Table 2. The mean of the AsymF was nearly zero, which means that there was no dominant asymmetry in the overall sample that could drive the results and thus individual differences in AsymF can be reliably examined in relation to other variables. *T*-tests revealed no difference between boys and girls in any of these variables.

Table 2. Descriptive values of the EEG frontal power asymmetry for the overall sample.

Variable (<i>N</i> = 25)	Mean (SD)	Range
1. LN right sites (F4, F8; μV^2)	1.37 (.37)	.67 – 2.13
2. LN left sites (F3, F7; μV^2)	1.41 (.42)	.58 – 2.16
3. EEG Frontal Asymmetry (Baseline; μV^2)	-.03 (.25)	(-.52) – (.57)

Correlation Analyses

Pearson correlation coefficients were computed among all of the predictor variables (i.e. variables 2-4 in Table 1 and variable 3 in Table 2) and peer preference, for the overall sample. Moreover, the correlations between variables 3-4 and 1, and 3-4 and 2 were also computed. The coefficients of all these correlations can be found in Table 3. As can be observed in the table, from the BIS factors, only the FFFS was significantly positively correlated with peer preference. Thus the more socially fearful (within a normal range) a child is, the more their peers will prefer that child. From the BAS factors, only the DRIVE was significantly negatively correlated with peer preference. Thus, the more persistently a child pursues his/her desired goals, the less their peers will prefer that child. Interestingly, almost all of the BIS/BAS ratios (i.e. BIS by BAS divisions) were significantly positively correlated with peer preference; the only non-significant correlation (i.e. BIS/REWRESP) was still marginally significant ($p = .08$). This result means that the higher the ratio between BIS and BAS factors (i.e. higher-than-the-BIS-mean BIS *and* lower-than-the-BAS-mean BAS), the higher the peer preference score. In other words, the more sensitive to punishment cues *and* the less driven to respond and approach to rewarding stimuli, the more preferred is a child. Importantly, the strongest correlations were seen for the correlations involving the FFFS. This result is also illustrated in Figure 2. Table 3 also shows that EEG frontal asymmetry in the alpha-band during baseline (AsymF) was significantly negatively correlated with only one factor among all five BIS/BAS factors, namely, Reward Responsiveness. Thus, the higher the AsymF, the lower is the responsiveness to reward. In other words, greater relative left-frontal baseline activity was associated with lower positive response to the occurrence or anticipation of rewards. Likewise, both BIS/BAS ratios involving reward responsiveness were also significantly positively correlated with AsymF, although the highest correlation was seen for the FFFS to Reward Responsiveness ratio. This result indicates that

greater relative left-frontal baseline activity is associated with higher social fear *and* lower response to reward. Importantly, contrary to expectations AsymF was not significantly related with peer preference. Finally, CIC (as measured by the peg tapping percentage of correct trials) was not significantly correlated with peer preference, AsymF, or with any of the BIS/BAS factors or BIS/BAS ratios.

Table 3. Correlations among all of the predictor variables of the study.

	Peer Preference	AsymF	CIC
Behavioral Inhibition System (BIS)			
Fight/Flight/Freezing System	.42*	.20	.04
Behavioral Inhibition System	.03	-.13	-.07
Behavioral Approach System (BAS)			
Reward Responsiveness	-.28	-.44***	-.10
Impulsivity/Fun Seeking	-.25	-.21	.003
Drive	-.37*	.06	.20
BIS/BAS (ratios)			
BIS to Reward Responsiveness	.27	.32*	.05
BIS to Impulsivity-Fun Seeking	.32**	.12	-.11
BIS to Drive	.31*	-.18	-.20
FFFS to Reward Responsiveness	.46***	.41**	.09
FFFS to Impulsivity-Fun Seeking	.44***	.23	.05
FFFS to Drive	.43**	.04	-.07
Cognitive Inhibitory Control (CIC)	.06	.20	-
EEG Frontal Asymmetry (AsymF)	.23	-	-

* p (one-tailed) < .06, ** p < .05; *** p < .01

Regression Analyses

A stepwise linear regression analysis was conducted to explore which of the predictor variables best explained the variance in peer preference Z-scores. Age, gender, and all predictor variables (including the BIS/BAS ratios) were entered in the model. The purpose of this analysis was to know which of the predictors better accounted for the variation in the peer preference scores. The analysis was conducted on the twenty-three subjects included in all of the previous analyses. This analysis yielded that the FFFS to Reward Responsiveness ratio significantly explained the variance in peer preference Z-scores, $R^2 = .22$, $F(1,21) = 6.03$, $p = .02$. Thus, the BIS/BAS ratio (specific to the ‘FFFS’ and ‘reward responsiveness’ factors) uniquely accounted for 22% of the variance ($\beta = .47$) in the peer preference scores of this sample of preschool children.

Figure 2. Plot that shows the BIS/BAS scores for each participant and his/her location in a 2 x 2 matrix of peer preference.

Red dots index participants with less than -1.0 in peer preference Z-score (i.e. the least preferred), while blue dots mean participants with ≥ -1.0 in this score (i.e. the most preferred). The numbers next to each dot mean the exact peer preference Z-score for each participant. The vertical and horizontal lines are respectively situated on the means of one of the BIS-factors (FFFS) and one of the BAS-factors (REWRESP) that are not significantly related with each other ($r = -.17$, $p = .18$). Each area in the plot represents a qualitative category of peer preference. X- and Y-axes scale means the possible score in the BIS (i.e. Sensitivity to Punishment) and BAS (i.e. Sensitivity to Reward) in the SPSRQ-C.

Discussion

This study examined the particular associations between two neurocognitive processes, CIC and BIS/BAS, and peer preference. This study further explored which of these two processes best explained the variance in peer preference in preschool children. With regard to the first goal, contrary to expectations CIC was not related with peer preference. By contrast, as expected, BIS was significantly positively associated with peer preference, whereas BAS was negatively associated with peer preference, indicating a balance between both with respect to peer preference. Specifically, only the BIS-factor ‘fight/flight/freeze system’ (FFFS) and only the BAS-factor ‘Drive’ were associated with peer preference. Likewise, almost all of the BIS/BAS ratios were significantly positively correlated with peer preference. However, contrary to expectations, EEG frontal activity was not significantly associated with peer preference. Finally, with respect to the second goal, the BIS/BAS (specifically the FFFS to Reward Responsiveness ratio) was the best predictor of peer preference, uniquely accounting for 22% of its variance.

Cognitive inhibitory control and peer preference

Cognitive Inhibitory Control (CIC) was not related with peer preference. In other words, it was not found that children with higher peer preference have higher CIC. This finding is unexpected because CIC is a central concept in theories of child cognitive and social development (Schachar & Logan, 1990) and because other studies have shown that executive functions in general, and CIC in particular, are significantly associated with specific skills of social competence, such as cooperative behaviors (e.g. Ciairano et al., 2007; Giannotta et al., 2011) or emotional regulation (Carlson & Wang, 2007). Thus it is possible that the socio-demographic homogeneity of this sample (i.e. same age and socioeconomic status) has obscured its variability in CIC performance, as the executive system is one of the primary neurocognitive systems sensitive to social factors in early experience (Lipina & Posner, 2012). Furthermore, preschoolers are more efficient in executive functioning when the task involves *another* individual who shares a common goal with them (Qu, 2011). Therefore, it is additionally possible that the social component of the task may have facilitated children’s performance.

Nevertheless, it is intriguing the fact that no correlation has been previously found between executive functions and (teacher-reported) social competence (Blair, 2003; Blair &

Peters, 2003) or between ‘non-social’ CIC tasks (e.g. a computer-based stop-signal task) and peer preference (Gomes & Livesey, 2008). Therefore, it is also likely that executive functions such as CIC, though affected by social components, fall within an entirely cognitive domain. Hence, variability in the cognitive domain would reflect variability in other cognitive aspects such as school readiness, but not necessarily in social competence. In fact, executive functioning does significantly positively predict academic outcomes (Diamond, Barnett, Thomas, & Munro, 2007). Furthermore, when social and emotional competence improves through special preschool curricula, cognitive abilities as inhibitory control, attention, or problem solving do not improve comparably (Domitrovich et al., 2007). In sum, due to either homogeneity of the sample, a social component of the task or an actual lack of correlation between CIC and peer preference, this study failed to show a correlation between CIC and peer preference.

BIS and BAS factors, and peer preference

With respect to BIS/BAS, as expected, BIS was significantly positively associated with peer preference, whereas BAS was negatively associated with peer preference. Specifically, on one side, the ‘fight/flight/freezing system’ factor of the Sensitivity to Punishment (i.e. BIS) scale of the SPSRQ-C was positively associated with peer preference. This result replicates previous findings using other BIS/BAS questionnaires (e.g. Carver & White, 1994) and other measures of social competence (i.e. teacher-reported; Blair, 2003). However, this study goes beyond previous studies by clarifying that it is the ‘social fear’ factor, and not the ‘general anxiety’ factor of BIS, what influences social competence the most in preschool children. This finding indicates that children who are more sensitive to signals of social punishment tend to be preferred more by their group peers. Blair (2003) had already explained that children who are more sensitive to this kind of signals might peacefully avoid conflict or not approach peers in a confrontational manner (Blair, 2003). It could indeed be that children do avoid conflict, because the fight/flight/freezing system is mainly responsible for active avoidance or escape from a threatening situation (cf. McNaughton & Corr, 2004). Additionally, on the other side, this study found a negative correlation between the ‘Drive’ factor of the Sensitivity to Reward (i.e. BAS) scale and peer preference. This relation has not been previously found when social competence has been measured through teacher’s report (e.g. Blair, 2003). Nevertheless, this finding indicates that preschool children who more persistently pursuit their desired goals are less preferred by group

peers. A likely explanation for this finding is that these children might share less and, consequently, their peers might perceive them as selfish or fussy, and thereby not like them. Although there is no direct evidence in this study that this is the case, one of the behaviors that typically characterizes preferred children is sharing (Dodge, 1983). Moreover, sharing requires set shifting (e.g. perceive others' needs), and this self-regulatory ability is actually negatively associated with BAS (Blair, Peters, & Granger, 2004). In sum, children who are more socially fearful *or* who can give up their desires tend to be more preferred in a group of peers.

BIS/BAS ratios and peer preference

The BIS/BAS model has proven to be a useful framework for understanding motivation (Amodio et al., 2008). For this reason this study decided to also analyze BIS in relation to BAS by calculating ratios between their factors' scores. Almost all of these ratios were significantly positively correlated with peer preference, such that any high BIS-factor *accompanied by* any low BAS-factor was associated with higher peer preference. This finding then indicates that the BIS/BAS ratios can also serve, above and beyond single factors, as correlates of peer preference. Importantly, the index to know what is a 'high' BIS or BAS and what is a 'low' BIS or BAS is the mean of the specific factor to be used (e.g. Luman et al., 2012). Thus, a BIS score above the mean for BIS *and* a BAS score below the mean for BAS are associated with higher peer preference. By contrast, a BIS score below the mean for BIS *and* a BAS score above the mean for BAS are associated with lower peer preference. Importantly, both BIS and BAS scores fell within the normal range. Therefore, these results do not indicate that having an extremely high BIS (i.e. sensitivity to punishment and aversive cues) and an extremely low BAS (i.e. sensitivity to reward and non-punishment cues) is associated with being more preferred among peers in a preschool group. Rather, these results must be interpreted within the context of typically developing preschool children. These findings make sense as activity in the BIS incites the individual to stop ongoing action and further scan the environment for more cues (e.g. if in a situation it is not clear whether to approach or to avoid), whereas activity in the BAS produces impulsive behavior towards reward with little attention to possible negative consequences (Muris, Meesters, de Kanter, & Timmerman, 2005). In sum, not only is being (somewhat) socially fearful important for peer preference in preschool, but especially being socially fearful *and* not being very much responsive to rewarding stimuli.

BIS/BAS measured through EEG frontal activity and peer preference

The EEG frontal asymmetry alpha-power during baseline (AsymF) can be used as a measure of BIS/BAS activity (Fox et al., 1996; Sutton & Davidson, 1997). Thus, in this study AsymF was examined in relation to peer preference. A negative correlation between greater relative left frontal activation and peer preference was expected. However, the correlation was non-significant and tended to be positive. In a previous study social competence was associated with greater relative left frontal activation (Fox et al., 1995). However, the measure of social competence used in such study was the proportion of time of engagement in sociodramatic play during one single session. In contrast, the peer preference metric used in the present study inherently relies upon *more than one* play or interactive session with peers along a preschool year. Thus more variability is inherent using peer preference instead of the behavior observed in one single play session. Therefore increasing the statistical power when using peer preference might enable us to find a significant effect. Finally, the previous study found a different direction of the correlation, such that greater left frontal activity was positively associated with social competence, whereas in the present study a negative correlation was hypothesized. The reason for this hypothesis is the positive correlation previously reported between BIS and social competence (e.g. Blair, 2003), and the possible negative correlation between BIS and greater left frontal activity.

EEG frontal asymmetry and reward responsiveness

In spite of the non-significant correlation between AsymF and peer preference, AsymF did significantly correlate with the 'Reward Responsiveness' factor of the BAS. More specifically, greater relative EEG left-frontal activity was associated with lower response to the occurrence or anticipation of rewards (i.e. low BAS). This result seems to contradict previous literature, because greater left-sided mid-frontal asymmetry is typically associated with higher BAS scores (e.g. in adults; Coan & Allen, 2003; Sutton & Davidson, 1997). Hence this result is puzzling. However, one possible explanation may reside in the emotional valence processing that also accompanies EEG resting frontal activity. In particular, greater relative left-frontal activity is associated with the propensity to respond with, and express, positive emotionality, while greater relative right-frontal activity is with negative emotionality, to the specific elicitors (Davidson &

Fox, 1982; Davidson & Tomarken, 1989; Pizzagalli, Sherwood, Henriques, & Davidson, 2005; Sutton & Davidson, 1997; Tomarken, Davidson, Wheeler, & Doss, 1992; Wheeler, Davidson, & Tomarken, 1993). Specifically, these associations represent individual differences in thresholds for affective responsivity when the respective elicitors occur (Davidson & Tomarken, 1989). Accordingly, our finding of greater relative left-frontal activity would indicate that children less responsive to reward might respond with positive affect to a non-occurrence of reward, while children more responsive to reward (because of this) are more prone to respond with, or express, negative affect to a non-occurrence of reward. This interpretation however needs empirical support. Nevertheless, this explanation is plausible as anticipating or seeking reward not always leads to its occurrence in a usual environment. Thus if children are continually expecting reward, they might become easily frustrated when they do not obtain it. In sum, the negative association between greater relative left-frontal resting activity and reward responsiveness indicates that children more responsive to reward are more prone to react with negative affect if the reward does not occur, while children less responsive to reward might react with less negative affect to the same situation.

Which of the two neurocognitive-processes, CIC and BIS/BAS, better predict peer preference?

With respect to the second goal, the BIS/BAS was the best predictor of peer preference. Specifically, the FFFS to Reward Responsiveness (REWRESP) ratio uniquely accounted for 22% of variance in peer preference scores. In accordance with the explanation of the correlations between the BIS/BAS ratios and peer preference, this finding indicates that an FFFS score above the FFFS-mean *in combination with* a Reward Responsiveness score below the REWRESP-mean significantly predicts a higher peer preference. Similarly, an FFFS score below the FFFS-mean *in combination with* a REWRESP score above the REWRESP-mean significantly predicts a lower peer preference. If both scores are concurrently above or below their respective means, then the peer preference can be ‘average’ (see Figure 2). As explained previously, children who are more socially ‘fearful’ in a typical range might avoid conflict. In addition, children who have less response to the anticipation and occurrence of rewards (e.g. as measured by items “Your child often does things to be praised” or “Your child generally prefer activities that involve immediate reward”; cf. Luman et al., 2012) might be better able to delay reward and not show negative affect when rewards are not obtained (also see AsymF results). Consequently, children

who avoid conflict *and* are better able to delay gratification may show less aggressive behavior and fewer negative responses when the expected rewards do not occur (i.e. tolerance to frustration), typical characteristics of the most preferred children (Dodge, 1983; Newcomb et al., 1993; Johnson et al., 2000).

Limitations and strengths

Some limitations are inherent to this study. First, an additional measure of CIC should have been used in order to more completely probe this ability (e.g. a stop signal task; Schachar & Logan, 1990). Although Luria's peg tapping task has been widely used with preschool populations to probe CIC, either its relatively low level of difficulty or its social component did not allow much variation in the performance of this specific sample. The use of a somewhat more heterogeneous sample would have also allowed more variation in performance with this task. Second, measures of the specific behaviors that CIC and BIS/BAS underlie would have been important to actually show that children do exhibit the behaviors that they 'should' according to their peer preference level. However, the relation between the specific behaviors and peer preference has been consistently shown since more than thirty years ago in different studies (e.g. Coie et al., 1982; Dodge, 1983). Third, it would have been much better to have a version of the SPSRQ-C specially designed for preschool children. However, this is not the case to date, and parents of children of this study did not report major difficulties filling out the questionnaire.

Fourth, alpha power was not reported separately for mid-frontal and lateral-frontal electrodes, which would have been interesting given that correlations might differ depending on the specific electrode sites (e.g. Coan & Allen, 2003). Fifth, another limitation inherent to the asymmetry calculation itself is that it does not allow to know whether the effect is due to hyperactivity of one hemisphere or hypoactivity of the other. Thus, literature should carefully be revised in order to apply a method that permits to explain the true source of the effect (e.g. Coan & Allen, 2003).

Finally, although the percentage of variance explained (i.e. R^2) by FFFS to reward responsiveness ratio was somewhat low, it is very similar to previously reported R^2 (e.g. Blair, 2003) and makes sense as other neurocognitive processes might also be associated with social competence in general, and peer preference in particular (e.g. theory of mind, action

understanding, cognitive flexibility, emotional regulation, etc.).

In spite of its limitations, this study reliably adds to the existing literature with three main findings. First, it is considering the BIS *in relation to* BAS (i.e. BIS/BAS ratio) what best predicts peer preference. Specifically, a high social fear *and* a low response to the occurrence or anticipation of reward (within a typical range) predict high peer preference. Second, this study clarifies that it is the fight/flight/freezing system (or active avoidance to threatening events), and not the behavioral inhibition system (or attentional engagement for the resolution of conflict between approaching or avoiding), as thought before, what influences the most social competence. Third, this study shows that response to reward is not necessarily related with general positive emotionality in preschool children, as evidenced by greater relative right-frontal neurophysiological activity during baseline.

Future directions

Future studies should either use both a social and a non-social task of similar level of difficulty to measure CIC in relation to peer preference or use a more heterogeneous sample with the peg-tapping task. Moreover, longitudinal studies using more heterogeneous samples might help to disentangle both whether BIS/BAS activity is present *before* the peer preference level is obtained and whether BIS/BAS activity is stable across development. Furthermore, future studies might also conduct intervention programs on BIS/BAS functioning to ascertain whether BIS/BAS activity causes the level of peer preference in preschool children. In addition, the analysis of EEG frontal asymmetry should be conducted separately for mid- and lateral-frontal electrodes and further associate it with an EEG measurement of the actual response to the occurrence and non-occurrence of expected rewards. Finally, the 5-factor model should be considered in future studies, as permits the differentiation between the effects of BIS ('general anxiety') and the effects of the FFFS ('social fear') in the social behavior of preschool children.

Conclusion

From the results of this study it can be concluded that BIS/BAS is more important than CIC for peer preference. In particular, within typical ranges, high social fear *and* low response to the anticipation and occurrence of reward significantly predicts higher peer preference. Thus the BIS

and BAS should not be considered separately, but in relation (e.g. using ratios between them) when they are to be used as predictors of social competence in general, and peer preference in particular. Interestingly, this study was able to show that successful relation with peers in preschool indeed requires a balance. However, this balance does not directly involve peers, but coping with both positive (i.e. rewarding) and negative (i.e. confrontational) environmental contingencies.

Acknowledgements

This study was possible thanks to the great supervision of Hinke Endedijk, Sabine Hunnius, and Eric Vuurman, to the worthy participation of hundreds of children—who very patiently understood my Dutch—and their parents, and to the invaluable help of Nadine Dijkstra in the measurement sessions, Marlene Meyer in the EEG recording and analysis, and all the other master's students who collaborated with the sociometric interviews. I also want to thank to my friends Andrea Reina and Maja Dobrosavljevic for helpful comments on earlier versions of this manuscript, as well as Carmen and Ron van Deursen for all their personal support during the writing process. Finally, nothing would have been possible without my faith and hope in God and without the solid and constant support of my beloved family: my mother, my sisters, and my partner Mario. Finally, I thank to Adrián Felipe, my nephew, because he is my source of inspiration and the stem of my interest in child research.

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Appendix

Sensitivity to Punishment and Sensitivity to Reward Questionnaire for Children (SPSRQ-C). Modified from Luman et al. (2012) to show the items that loaded in each factor of the 5-factor solution for this questionnaire.

Sensitivity to Punishment (BIS) scale

'Fight/Flight/Freezing System' factor items

2. Your child prefers not to ask for something when they are not sure they will obtain
4. Your child enjoys being the center of attention (reverse)
5. Your child is a shy person
7. Whenever possible, your child avoids demonstrating their skills for fear of being embarrassed
9. When in a group, your child has difficulty thinking of something to say
18. It is difficult for your child to talk with someone they do not know
19. Your child generally tries to avoid speaking in groups
29. Your child often refrains from doing something because of fear of being embarrassed

'Behavioral Inhibition System' factor items

12. Your child is often afraid of new or unexpected situations
15. Whenever they can, your child avoids going to unfamiliar places
17. Your child often worries about things they said or did
20. Your child has a lot of difficulty ending a fun activity
21. Your child could do more things if it were not for their fear
23. Your child is afraid of many things compared to other children their age
24. Your child has difficulty staying focused on their school work in the presence of an attractive alternative
31. If your child thinks that something unpleasant is going to happen, they get pretty worked up
33. Criticism or scolding hurts your child very much

Sensitivity to Reward (BAS) scale

'Reward Responsiveness' factor items

1. The good prospect of obtaining a reward motivates your child strongly to do some things
3. Your child often does things to be praised
8. When your child gets something they want, they feel excited and energized
10. Your child does a lot of things for approval
13. Does your child generally prefer activities that involve immediate reward
22. Your child sometimes does things for quick reward

'Impulsiveness/ Fun Seeking' factor items

11. The possibility of obtaining social status moves your child to action, even if this involves not playing fair
14. Your child often has trouble resisting the temptation of doing forbidden things
25. Your child engages in risky behavior to obtain a reward
26. Your child often refrains from doing something they like in order not to be rejected or disapproved of by others

'Drive' factor items

- 6. When your child is in a group, they try to stand out as the smartest or the funniest
- 16. Your child likes to compete and do everything they can to win
- 27. Your child likes competitive activities
- 28. Your child would like to be a socially powerful person
- 30. Your child likes displaying their physical abilities even though it may involve danger
- 32. Your child craves excitement and new sensations